

Effect of Land Use-Type on Soil Physical Properties Under Six Different Plantations

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Abstract

The effects of land use type (LUT) on the physicochemical properties of the soils of mango plantations (MPs), Neem plantations (NPs), arable farms (AFs), vegetable farms (FFs), flood plains (FPs), and residential areas (RAs) were evaluated from November-December 2022. Soil samples were collected from the ecological zone of Nigeria Sudan, which is Borno. To understand the drastic changes in land use types and their effects on ecosystems, investigations are required to explore the extent to which LUT affects soil properties in arid environments. Samples were collected at predetermined depths of 0-20 and 20-40 cm in all the LUTs. The samples were subjected to laboratory analysis and statistical tools such as Factorial (ANOVA) and Means Separations using (LSD) at a 0.05% probability level. Analysis of the effects of LUT and depth on soil particle size revealed that VFs had more sand and fewer FPs, with values of 70.30% and 55.30%, respectively; FPs had more silt and fewer AFs, with values of 30.833% and 14.583%, respectively; and AFs had more clay and fewer VFs, with values of 18.033% and 11.783%, respectively. There were no differences in the soil characteristics, and the soil textures were sandy loam for all the LUTs. BD, TP, WHC, MWD, θ , PR, and MC ranged from 1.37–1.46 g/cm², 44.67–48.5%, 21.23–29.70%, 0.077–0.1515 mm, 26.733–36.017°C, 20.833–29.333 N/cm and 0.1543–0.3303 cm³/cm³, respectively, with the greatest ranges found for VF-AF, AF-VF, MP-FP, RA-VF, VF-RA, VF-AF and RA-VF, respectively. Based on these findings, the 20-40 cm soil layer was best for all the LUTs. This study showed that land use type can affect soil physical properties. Therefore, vegetable farms and Neem plantations at depths of 20-40 cm were recommended for the study area.

Keywords: land, land use type, soil, soil physical properties, plantation

Introduction

Land use is a term used to describe the human use of land and is defined as the arrangements, activities, and inputs people undertake in a certain land cover type to produce, change, or maintain it (Ufot et al., 2016). It represents the economic and cultural activities (e.g., agricultural, residential, industrial, mining, and recreational uses) that are practiced at a given place (EPA, 2020). Successful agriculture requires the sustainable use of soil resources because soil can easily lose its quality and quantity within a short period for different reasons, such as intensive cultivation, leaching, and soil erosion (Kiflu et al., 2013). Agricultural practices, therefore, require basic knowledge of the sustainable use of land (Takele et al., 2014). The success of soil management in maintaining soil quality depends on understanding how the soil responds to agricultural practices over time (Duguma et al., 2010). Land use types are a process by which human activities transform the natural landscape, referring to how the land has been used, usually emphasizing the functional role of land for economic activities (Paul, et al., 2017). Land use types can affect several soil properties depending on the intensity and type of use, and some of the physical properties of soil may be modified (e.g., structure, consistency, bulk density, porosity, aggregate stability, moisture content, particle size and texture) (Paz González et al., 2014). The physical properties of soil include color, texture, structure, porosity, density, consistency, temperature, and air (Usman, 2013). The physical properties of the soil are very important for agricultural production and the sustainable use of soil. The amount and rate of water, oxygen, and nutrient absorption by plants depend on the ability of the roots to absorb the soil solution as well as the ability of the soil to supply it to the roots (Almendro et al., 2018). Information about the effects of different land use types on soil physical and chemical properties is crucial for best land management practices (Girma, 2020). Knowledge of soil properties is very useful for determining soil characteristics, quality, and productivity (Akinde et al., 2020). The information gathered in this study will provide useful feedback to farmers, extension agents, and the government on land use design and implementation. It is also expected that the results will be useful to government and extension service providers in planning, designing, and evaluating effective and efficient agricultural policies, programs, and projects at local, regional, and national scales for smallholder farmers in the semiarid tropics of Sub-Saharan Africa (Mzezewa et al., 2011). Understanding soil properties under different land use types is vital for determining the types of soil management practices that could be implemented by smallholder farmers to improve soil health as well as soil productivity. It is also important in addressing the issues of agricultural sustainability (Negasa et al., 2017). Inappropriate land use leads to the deterioration of potential productivity, including ecological functioning and ecosystem services (Alaboz et al., 2021). Soil properties can be influenced by long-term agricultural management practices, as described in the pedological literature (Vopravil et al., 2020). Land use types have long been considered among the many factors responsible for physical and chemical soil degradation (Fentie et al., 2020). This paper assesses the effect of land use-type on soil physical properties in Jere agricultural area of Borno State Nigeria.

Materials and methods

Study area

The study was conducted in Gongulong-Meyerari agricultural area located in Jere, local government of Borno State, Nigeria. The area is positioned along the coast of the Ngada River where vegetable crops are grown annually for commercial purposes (van Herk, 2012). The area falls within the 11.923100°N and 13.221758°E of Borno State (Figure 1). It is characterized by biannual mean rainfall and temperatures of 650mm and 32°C respectively. The months of March and April are the hottest periods of the year, with monthly temperatures ranging between 30°C and 40°C. The volcanic and basement complex areas of the region have fertile clayey loamy soils in valley bottoms, but skeletal soils and rock outcrops occur along gentle and steep slopes (van Herk, 2012). The vegetation accommodated plants such as *Mangifera indica*, *Acacia nilotica*, *Acacia senegal*, *Acacia seyal*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Ziziphus* spp. and *Balanites aegyptiaca*.

Figure 1. Areal map of the study area

Site Selection and Soil Sampling

The methodology consisted of primary recognition and pre-assessment site visits for defining land use types. A random-systematic method was used for soil sampling in key areas of each land use type in 2022. First, the study area was divided into six land use systems (residential land, arable farms, vegetable farms, floodplain land, mango plantations, and Neem plantations). For each land use, soil samples were obtained at a constant depth 0 - 40 cm at 20 intervals following a Z layout design. Approximately 1 kg of composite samples were collected from each land use and placed in polythene bags. For each adjacent land use, composite soil samples were collected 0 – 20 from random soil subsamples within 40 cm depth using a hand auger for four replications. For the determination of bulk density, thirty-six undisturbed soil samples were also collected using a core sampler at the site, and thirty-six samples were collected for each land use type.

Laboratory analysis

The soil particle size distribution was analysed using the hydrometric method (Bouyoucos, 1962). Soil bulk density (BD) was determined from undisturbed soil samples collected using a core sampler (Blake, 1986). Total porosity (TP) was calculated from the values of bulk density (BD) and particle density (PD) (Brady, 2008). The moisture content was determined using the gravimetric method (Black, 2005). Aggregate stability is an important property and can be measured as dry aggregate stability, and the mean weight diameter (MWD) is calculated by the method suggested by Yoder (1936) and Youker and McGuinness (1957). A concrete penetrometer is used to determine the penetration resistance of soil in fields (Biologydiscussion, 2020). The water holding capacity was determined according to the methods of Biologydiscussion (2020).

Results

Effects of land use type and depth on the soil particle size analysis

Table 1 gives the results of the effects of land use type and depth on the soil particle size analysis. There is inequality ($p \leq 0.05$) in the effects of land use type and depth on the soil particle size. Similarly, there was a significant difference in the effects of land use types on sand; the highest value was recorded for a vegetable farm, with a value of 70.30%, and the lowest value was obtained for a flood plain, with a value of 55.30%. However, there was no significant difference in the effects of depth on the sand; the highest value was recorded at a depth of 0-20 cm, with a value of 63.906%, and the lowest value was obtained at a depth of 20-40 cm, with a value of 63.667%, although there was numerical variation across the depths.

Table 1. *Effects of land use types and Depth on Particles size analysis Jere*

Land use types	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Textural class
Arable Farm	67.383 ^a	14.583 ^c	18.034 ^a	Sandy loam
Flood Plain	55.3 ^b	30.833 ^a	13.867 ^b	Sandy loam
Mango Plantation	66.133 ^a	21.667 ^b	12.2 ^b	Sandy loam
Neem Plantation	66.633 ^a	19.217 ^{bc}	14.15 ^b	Sandy loam
Residential Area	56.967 ^b	29.167 ^a	13.866 ^b	Sandy loam
Vegetable Farm	70.3 ^a	17.917 ^{bc}	11.78b ^b	Sandy loam
LSD (0.05)	5.7721	5.1341	4.367	
SE±	2.8178	2.5064	1.864	
Depth (cm)				
0-20	63.906 ^a	21.961 ^a	14.133 ^a	Sandy loam
20-40	63.667 ^a	22.5 ^a	13.833 ^a	Sandy loam
LSD (0.05)	5.0803	5.0593	0.986	
SE±	2.4941	2.4838	0.579	

*=significant at 5% LSD= least significant difference and LUT= land use type

Nonetheless, there was a significant difference in the effects of land use types on silt; the highest value was observed on a flood plain, with a value of 30.833%, and the lowest value was obtained on an arable farm, with a value of 14.583%. There was no variation in the effects of depth on silt; the greatest difference was recorded at depths of 20-40 cm, with a value of 22.500%, and the lowest difference was obtained at depths of 0-20 cm, with a value of 21.961%. There was a significant difference in the effects of land use type on clay; the

highest value was recorded for an arable farm, with a value of 18.033%, and the lowest value was obtained for a vegetable farm, with a value of 11.783%. There was no significant difference in the effects of depth on the clay content; the highest value of 14.122% was recorded at depths ranging from 0-20 cm, and the lowest value of 13.833% was observed at depths ranging from 20-40 cm. The textural class was sandy loam for all land use types.

Effects of land use type and depth on the soil physical properties of Jere

The results on the effects of land use type and depth on soil physical properties are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Effects of Land use types and Depth on Soil Physical Properties of Jere*

Land use types	Pb (g/cm ²)	%TP	%WHC	MWD (mm)	Temp (°C)	P.R (N/A)	θ _v (cm ³ /cm ³)
Arable Farm	1.4617 ^a	44.667 ^d	21.90 ^{bc}	0.0825 ^{cd}	35.517 ^{ab}	29.333 ^a	0.1563 ^b
Flood Plain	1.395 ^{cd}	47.333 ^{ab}	29.70 ^a	0.129 ^{7b}	33.983 ^{bc}	25.50 ^a	0.1938 ^b
Mango Plantation	1.4533 ^{ab}	45.00 ^{cd}	21.233 ^c	0.0743 ^d	30.267 ^d	25.333 ^a	0.1997 ^b
Neem Plantation	1.4167 ^{bc}	46.667 ^{bc}	24.05 ^b	0.1023 ^c	33.15 ^c	26.00 ^a	0.1692 ^b
Residential Area	1.43 ^{abc}	45.833 ^{bcd}	22.75 ^{bc}	0.077 ^d	36.017 ^a	29.167 ^a	0.1543 ^b
Vegetable Farm	1.37 ^d	48.50 ^a	22.583 ^{bc}	0.1515 ^a	26.733 ^e	20.833 ^a	0.3303 ^a
LSD Value	0.0424	1.6972	2.7199	0.0210	1.8213	15.072	0.0554
SE±	0.0207	0.8286	1.3278	0.0102	0.8891	7.3577	0.0271
Depth (cm)							
0-20	1.4617 ^a	44.667 ^b	35.517 ^a	0.1563 ^b	21.9 ^b	29.333 ^a	0.0825 ^b
20-40	1.395 ^b	47.333 ^a	33.983 ^b	0.1938 ^a	29.7 ^a	25.5 ^a	0.1297 ^a
LSD Value	0.0424	1.6972	1.8213	0.0554	2.7199	15.072	0.0210
SE±	0.0207	0.8286	0.8891	0.0271	1.3278	7.3577	0.0102

Pb=bulk density, TP=total porosity, WHC=water holding capacity, MDW=mean weight diameter, PR=penetration resistance, θ_v=volume moisture content, LSD=large difference and SE=standard error, LUT=land use type.

The results revealed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the effects of land use type and depth on the soil physical properties. There was a relationship in the effects of land use type and depth on the bulk density; the highest values were recorded at arable farms and depths of 20-40 cm (1.4617 g/cm³ and 1.4489 g/cm³, respectively), and the lowest values were obtained at vegetable farms and depths of 0-20 cm (1.3700 g/cm² and 1.3933 g/cm², respectively). The bulk density in undisturbed soils ranges from approximately 1.0 to 1.45 g/cm³, which is normal for sandy loam soil and increases with depth in the soil profile (Kozłowski 1999). However, there was no relationship in the effects of land use type and depth on the total porosity; the highest values were recorded at vegetable farms and depths of 0-20 cm (48.500% and 47.444%, respectively), and the lowest values were obtained at arable farms and depths of 20-40 cm (44.667% and 45.222%, respectively).

In general, the total porosity of unconsolidated materials ranges from 0.25-0.7 (25%-70%). Coarse-textured soil materials such as gravel and sand tend to have a lower total

porosity than fine-textured soils such as silts and clays. The total porosity in soils is not constant because the soil, particularly clayey soil, alternately swells, shrinks, compacts, and cracks (Yu *et al.*, 1993).

Likewise, there was dissimilarity in the effects of land use type and depth on the water holding capacity. The highest values were recorded for the flood plain and at depths of 0-20 cm (29.700% and 25.011%, respectively), and the lowest values were obtained for the mango plantation and at depths of 20-40 cm (21.233% and 22.394%, respectively). There was a high variability in the effects of land use type and depth on the mean weight diameter; the greatest difference was recorded at vegetable farms and depths of 0-20 mm (0.1515 mm and 0.1094 mm, respectively), and the lowest difference was observed at mango plantations and depths of 20-40 cm (0.0743 mm and 0.0964 mm, respectively).

Soils with MWDs greater than 0.25 mm are considered good for crop production (Phogat, 2016). The results also show that there was an inconsistency in the effects of land use type and depth on the soil temperature; the highest values were recorded in the residential area and at depths of 0-20 cm (36.01°C and 33.77°C, respectively), and the lowest values were obtained at the vegetable farm and at depths of 20-40 cm (26.73°C and 31.45°C, respectively).

The daily soil temperature for clayey soil ranges from 27.7–28.90°C, with a simple mean of 28.3°C; the daily soil temperature ranges from 28.2–29.10°C for sandy soil and from 28.3–34.00°C for loamy soil. The mean temperature for all soil types is 29.70°C, indicating that these soils are favourable for farming (Nwankwo, 2012). In the same way also, there was a difference in the effects of land use type and depth on soil penetration resistance; the highest values were recorded at arable farms and depths of 0-20 cm (29.333 and 37.167, respectively), and the lowest values were obtained at vegetable farms and depths of 20-40 cm (20.833 N/A and 14.889 N/A, respectively).

Likewise, there was a variation in the effects of land use type and depth on the soil moisture content; the highest values were recorded at vegetable farms and depths of 20-40 cm (0.3303 cm³/cm³ and 0.2365 cm³/cm³, respectively), and the lowest values were obtained at arable farms and depths of 0-20 cm (0.1543 cm³/cm³ and 0.1647 cm³/cm³, respectively). The volumetric soil moisture content remaining at field capacity is approximately 0.15 to 0.25 cm³/cm³ for sandy soils, 0.35 to 0.45 cm³/cm³ for loam soils, and 0.45 to 0.55 cm³/cm³ for clay soils.

Interaction effects between land use type and depth on the soil physical properties

The results of the interactive effects between land use type and depth on soil physical properties are presented in Table 4. The results revealed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the interactive effects of land use type and depth on the soil physical properties of Jere. There was a variation in the interactive effects of land use type and depth on the bulk density, total porosity and water holding capacity. The highest values were recorded at the Mango Plantation site at depths ranging from 20-40, at the Vegetable Farm site at depths ranging from 0-20 and at the Flood Plain site at depths ranging from 0-20, with values ranging from 1.50 g/cm², 49.00% and 30.53%, respectively, and the lowest values were obtained at the Vegetable Farm, Mango Plantation site at depths ranging from 20-40, 0-20

and Vegetable Farm site at depths ranging from 20-40, with values ranging from 1.38 g/cm², 43.33% and 19.57%, respectively.

There was a disparity in the interactive effects of land use type and depth on the mean weight diameter, soil temperature and soil penetration resistance. The highest values were recorded at a vegetable farm with depths of 0-20, residential area depths of 0-20 and residential areas with depths of 0-20 with values of 0.16 mm, 37.40°C and 40.00 N/cm, respectively, and the lowest values were obtained at residential areas with depths of 20-40, vegetable farms with depths of 20-40 and vegetable farms with depths of 20-40 with values of 0.07 mm, 25.37°C and 9.00 N/cm, respectively. There was a discrepancy in the interactive effects of land use type and depth on the soil moisture content; the highest value was recorded at a vegetable farm with a depth of 20-40 cm/cm³, with a value of 0.35 cm³/cm³, and the lowest value was obtained at an arable farm with a depth of 0-20 cm³/cm³.

Discussion

The greatest range of particle sizes was found in the flood plain as a result of soil deposited by erosion, and most of the soils in the arid region were recently formed soil and sandy. This is supported by Girma (2020). The soil textures of the different land use systems are sandy loam, sandy clay loam and loam. In all the land use systems, the sand fraction was dominant, ranging from 40% - 61%. In all land use systems, the sand fraction is dominant, ranging from 40% - 61% in arid regions (Geetha et al., 2021). A high bulk density was found in the residential area, and the 20-40 cm depth was affected by a low soil organic matter content, which promoted soil compaction. This is supported by Girma (2020), who reported that the high bulk density recorded under residential land, which increases with depth, might be a result of low organic matter content, increased soil disturbance, and compaction from the repeated movement of load, and the downwards increase in the soil bulk density might be explained by more compaction by less root penetration in the overlying soil and lower soil organic matter in the subsurface layer.

The highest range of total porosity was found at the vegetable farm, and the 0-20 cm depth was affected by the high organic manure content and minimum tillage. These findings are in line with those of Asmare et al. (2023), who reported high porosity in a vegetable farm as a result of an increase in soil organic matter. The highest water holding capacity was found on the flood plain, and the 0-20 cm depth was a result of the high clay and organic matter contents. This finding was in line with previous findings (Asmare et al., 2023). A higher MWD was observed at the vegetable farm, and the 20-40 cm depth was a result of the high organic manure content and minimum tillage. These findings are in line with those of Asmare et al. (2023). The higher soil temperature in the residential area at 20-40 cm was a result of a low soil organic matter content and compaction as supported by Girma (2020). However, the higher soil penetration resistance found in the residential area and at depths of 20-40 cm was a result of the low soil organic matter content and compaction.

Table 4. Interaction effects of Land use types and Depth on Soil Physical Properties

Land use types	Depth (cm)	Pb (g/cm ²)	%TP	%WHC	MWD(mm)	Temp(C ^o)	P.R (N/A)	θ _v (cm ³ /cm ³)
Arable Farm	0-20	1.43 ^{cd}	46.00 ^{de}	22.63 ^{cd}	0.09 ^{ef}	36.83 ^a	39.67 ^a	0.11 ^g
	20-40	1.49 ^a	43.33 ^g	21.17 ^{de}	0.07 ^f	34.20 ^b	19.00 ^e	0.20 ^{de}
Flood Plain	0-20	1.38 ^f	48.00 ^b	30.53 ^a	0.14 ^{abc}	34.60 ^b	38.33 ^{ab}	0.12 ^{fg}
	20-40	1.41 ^{de}	46.67 ^{cd}	28.87 ^a	0.12 ^{bcd}	33.37 ^{bc}	12.67 ^h	0.26 ^c
Mango Plantation	0-20	1.41 ^{de}	46.67 ^{cd}	21.73 ^{cde}	0.08 ^{ef}	31.63 ^d	36.67 ^{bc}	0.19 ^{de}
	20-40	1.50 ^a	43.33 ^g	20.73 ^{de}	0.07 ^f	28.90 ^e	14.00 ^{gh}	0.21 ^d
Neem Plantation	0-20	1.39 ^{ef}	47.667 ^b	25.53 ^b	0.1 ^{cde}	34.07 ^b	35.67 ^c	0.13 ^f
	20-40	1.44 ^c	45.67 ^e	22.57 ^{cd}	0.10 ^{def}	32.23 ^{cd}	16.33 ^{fg}	0.20 ^{de}
Residential Area	0-20	1.39 ^{ef}	47.33 ^{bc}	24.03 ^{bc}	0.08 ^{ef}	37.40 ^a	40.00 ^a	0.12 ^{fg}
	20-40	1.47 ^b	44.33 ^f	21.47 ^{cde}	0.07 ^f	34.63 ^b	18.33 ^{ef}	0.19 ^e
Vegetable Farm	0-20	1.36 ^g	49.00 ^a	25.60 ^b	0.16 ^a	28.10 ^e	32.67 ^d	0.31 ^b
	20-40	1.38 ^f	48.00 ^b	19.57 ^e	0.15 ^{ab}	25.37 ^f	9.00 ⁱ	0.35 ^a
LSD (0.05)		0.02	0.93	2.83	0.03	1.39	2.37	0.02
SE±		0.01	0.45	1.36	0.015	0.67	1.14	6.27E-03

Pb=Bulk Density, TP=Total Porosity, WHC=Water Holding Capacity, MDW= Mean Weight Diameter, PR=Penetration Resistant, θ_v=Volumetric Moisture Content, LSD=Least Significant Difference and SE= Standard Error LUT= Land use types. The mean values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% probability level.

This is supported by the findings of Jal et al. (2020) and Girma (2020), who reported that the highest penetration resistance recorded under residential land might be linked to low organic matter content, increased soil disturbance, and compaction from the repeated movement of load. Higher soil moisture content was found on the vegetable farm and at depths of 20-40 cm as a result of the high organic manure content and minimum tillage. This finding was in line with that of Asmare et al. (2023).

Conclusion

This study revealed inconsistency in soil properties among the different land use types. This study revealed that the study of land use types and their impacts will greatly help planning work and will reveal future planning methods. Thus, the understanding of land use types should be strongly intensified for ecosystem management and sustainability. This research showed that, compared with other land use types, plantations restore good soil physical and chemical properties. Based on these findings, Neem Plantations and Vegetable Farm had good soil physical properties at different soil depths. The following recommendations have been highlighted for sustainable land use in the study area.

- a. Since the soil of the study areas under different land use types is well understood, proper management practices and land use management techniques, such as the planting of more trees and the proper use of animal dung, should be encouraged.
- b. Vegetable farms and need plantations should be considered to improve the soil physical properties of the study area.

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